

Performance Enhancement of Microstrip Patch Antenna With Slots for 5G Communication

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Abstract— The demand for high-performance antennas tailored for 5G applications has spurred research into novel designs and optimization techniques. This study focuses on the design, development, and optimization of MPA (microstrip patch antennas) integrated with slots to enhance their performance in 5G communication systems. Various slot configurations, including rectangular and T-shaped slots, are incorporated into the ground plane of the patch antennas to investigate their impact on antenna characteristics such as gain, bandwidth, and radiation pattern. Simulation results demonstrate that the introduction of slots effectively increases the antenna's effective aperture, modifies current distribution, and enhances radiation efficiency. Furthermore, the strategic placement of slots improves antenna directivity and suppresses surface waves, leading to a notable improvement in antenna gain. Experimental validation corroborates the simulation findings, showcasing the practical feasibility and efficiency of the proposed slot-integrated antenna designs. Overall, this research contributes to the advancement of antenna technology tailored for the evolving requirements of 5G communication systems.

Keywords— Microstrip patch antenna, 5G, mm Wave, FR4 epoxy, reflection coefficient.

I. INTRODUCTION

Antennas are the unsung heroes of the wireless world, quietly enabling the seamless exchange of information that underpins modern communication systems. From the towering structures of broadcast towers to the minuscule components embedded within our smartphones, antennas come in all shapes and sizes, serving a multitude of purposes across various applications. At their essence, antennas are devices designed to transmit and receive electromagnetic waves. They are the bridge between the physical world and the invisible realm of radio frequencies, allowing us to communicate over vast distances, access the internet, navigate with GPS, and even explore the depths of space.

Throughout this journey, we will uncover the challenges and opportunities inherent in antenna design, from overcoming interference and propagation issues to pushing the boundaries of miniaturization and integration. And ultimately, we will gain a deeper appreciation for the vital role that antennas play in shaping the way we communicate, connect, and interact in today's wireless world.

II. MICROSTRIP PATCH ANTENNA

A. Introduction

Microstrip patch antennas represent a fascinating intersection of simplicity and sophistication in the realm of antenna design. These compact and versatile devices have found extensive use in a plethora of applications, ranging from satellite communication and radar systems to wireless networks and RFID tags. At first glance, a MPA appears deceptively simple—a flat, rectangular patch of conductive material mounted on a dielectric substrate. However, beneath this seemingly straightforward structure lies a rich tapestry of electromagnetic principles and engineering ingenuity. The MPA owes its popularity to several key advantages. Its low profile and planar geometry make it easy to fabricate, integrate, and deploy in various systems. Additionally, its scalability allows for customization across a broad range of frequencies and applications, from microwave to millimetre-wave frequencies.

Fig 1. Microstrip patch antenna

B. Types of MPA

Microstrip patch antennas come in various types and configurations, each tailored to specific applications and performance requirements. Here are some common types:

Rectangular Microstrip Patch Antenna: This is the most basic form of MPA, consisting of a rectangular patch of conductive material on a dielectric substrate.

Circular Microstrip Patch Antenna: Instead of a rectangular shape, this antenna features a circular or annular patch. Circular patches offer advantages such as wider

bandwidth and improved radiation characteristics compared to their rectangular counterparts.

Dual-polarized Microstrip Patch Antenna: These antennas are designed to radiate or receive two orthogonal polarizations simultaneously. They are commonly used in satellite communication, radar systems, and MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) wireless communication systems.

Dual-band Microstrip Patch Antenna: Dual-band antennas radiates at two distinct frequencies or frequency bands. These antennas are designed with specialized structures or feeding techniques to achieve resonance at multiple frequencies, enabling compatibility with multi-band communication systems.

Circularly Polarized Microstrip Patch Antenna: Circularly polarized antennas are designed [11] to radiate or receive electromagnetic waves with circular polarization. They find applications in satellite communication, RFID systems, and GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) antennas.

These are just a few examples of the types of MPAs available. Each type offers unique advantages and trade-offs, and the choice depends on factors such as frequency requirements, bandwidth, size constraints, and environmental considerations.

III. BASIC PARAMETER ANALYSIS OF MPA

An antenna is a transformer between a transmission line and free space. To describe an antenna, we must characterize its properties as a transmission line load (input impedance) and the distribution of the electromagnetic energy that it radiates into space (radiation pattern). There are a number of key parameters and concepts that we can use to describe antenna properties.

A. Antenna parameters

Resonant Frequency: An antenna's electrical length is correlated with its "resonant frequency" and "electrical resonance". Typically, the electrical length of a wire is calculated by dividing its physical length by its velocity factor, which is the ratio of the wire's wave propagation speed to c_0 , the speed of light in a vacuum. An antenna works well for a range of frequencies that are typically centered on that resonant frequency since it is typically tuned for that particular frequency. The radiation pattern and impedance, in particular, are two characteristics of an antenna that vary with frequency; hence, the resonant frequency of the antenna may only be near the centre frequency of these other, more significant characteristics. [10]

It is possible to make antennas resonant at harmonic frequencies by using lengths that are smaller than the desired wavelength. While certain antenna designs are comparatively successful throughout a wide range of frequencies, others have several resonance frequencies. The logarithmic or log periodic wide band aerial is the most widely recognized variety; nonetheless, its gain is typically significantly less than that of a particular or narrower band aerial. [10]

Return loss: Optical fibre is the data carrier of choice compared to copper wire. Fiber optic networks have exponentially higher capacity, experience no crosstalk, and

can be installed in areas with high electromagnetic interference such as along utility and power lines.

Return loss or reflection loss is the reflection of signal power from the insertion of a device in a transmission line or optical fibre. It is expressed as ratio in dB relative to the transmitted signal power.

Fig 2. Return loss

The return loss is given by:

$$RL \text{ dB} = 10 \log Pr/Pi \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where P_i is power supplied by the source and P_r is the power reflected. If V_i is the amplitude of the incident wave and V_r that of the reflected wave, then the return loss can be expressed in terms of the reflection coefficient r as: $RL = -20|r|$ and the reflection coefficient r can be expressed as; $r = V_r/V_i$.

For an antenna to radiate effectively, the return loss should be less than -10 dB [4]. For example, for frequency 1.9 GHz , a simple RL curve is shown in Fig. 3

Fig 3. RL curve of an antenna

Radiation Pattern: An antenna radiation pattern or antenna pattern is defined as –a mathematical function or a graphical representation of the radiation properties of the antenna as a function of space coordinates. In most cases, the radiation pattern is determined in the far field region and is represented as a function of the directional coordinates. The radiation from an antenna can be explained with the help of figure 2.9 which shows a voltage source connected to a two conductor transmission line.

Fig 4. Radiation Mechanism of an Antenna.

A particular far field radiation pattern is produced by the patch's radiation at the bordering fields. This radiation pattern demonstrates that the antenna emits more power in one direction relative to another. The direction perpendicular to the rectangular patch (broadside) is where the patch's maximal directivity occurs when it is activated in its basic mode. In the direction of lower heights and away from the broadside, the directivity diminishes. Below is an illustration of a radiation pattern.

Fig 5: Typical radiation pattern of a simple square patch [2].

B. Feeding techniques

Microstrip Feed: This involves connecting the patch element to a microstrip transmission line, typically placed on the same substrate as the patch. The feed line is usually designed to provide the desired impedance matching and control the antenna's resonant frequency.

Coaxial Feed: Coaxial feeding involves connecting the antenna to a coaxial cable, where the inner conductor of the cable is connected to the patch element, and the outer conductor serves as the ground plane.

Inset Feed: In inset feeding, the transmission line is directly connected to the patch element at a specific location along its edge.

Proximity Feed: Proximity feeding involves placing the transmission line close to the patch element without direct physical contact.

Aperture Coupled Feed: Aperture coupling involves coupling energy from the feed line to the patch element

through an aperture in the ground plane beneath the patch.

Probe Feed: Probe feeding utilizes a metallic probe inserted through the substrate to make contact with the patch element.

Balanced Feed: Balanced feeding involves using a balanced transmission line, such as a microstrip line or a strip line, to deliver energy to the antenna.

C. Design Equations

An initial guess at the patch width:

$$[1] \quad W = \frac{c_0}{2f_r} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\epsilon_r + 1}}, \quad c_0 \text{ is speed of light} \quad \dots\dots(2)$$

Find effective parameters:

$$[2] \quad \epsilon_{reff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W} \right]^{-1/2}, \quad W/h > 1 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$[3] \quad \frac{\Delta L}{h} = 0.412 \frac{(\epsilon_{reff} + 0.3) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.264 \right)}{(\epsilon_{reff} - 0.258) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.8 \right)} \quad \dots\dots (4)$$

Get patch length:

$$[4] \quad L = \frac{c_0}{2f_r \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} - 2\Delta L \quad \dots\dots (5)$$

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study's main goal was to determine how dielectric superstrates and a single slot affected a number of performance parameters, including input impedance, return loss, bandwidth, beamwidth, gain, resonance frequency, and VSWR [1].

A rectangular microstrip patch antenna intended for 2.6348 GHz operation is shown in this research. The antenna has a horizontal slot and a U-slot to efficiently reduce cross-polarization. The antenna obtains improved radiation characteristics by carefully positioning the U-slot on the radiating patch and adding a horizontal slot to the patch [2].

This research proposes a slotted rectangular microstrip patch antenna based on nanomaterials for WLAN applications, with the goal of improving gain and bandwidth. Nanomaterial is initially deposited in the slot area of a conventional copper rectangular microstrip antenna (MSA) that has a rectangular slot in the patch area. Gold nanoparticles (Au NPs) and a mixture of silver-gold-silver nanoparticles (Ag-Au-Ag NPs) are used to deposit two types of metallic nanoparticulate thin films in the slot region, after which the antenna parameters are examined. A contrast is shown between the manufactured antenna using the two

distinct nanoparticulate thin films and the traditional slotted MSA [3].

This study focuses on the high-band millimetre waves of 5G, with a special emphasis on the extensively used frequency bands of 26 and 28 GHz. The primary objective of this work is to create slots with L and I forms to a single rectangular patch, a structure that is frequently utilized in 5G antennas, in order to significantly increase the gain of the microstrip patch antenna. It is important to note that the CST Studio Suite simulator was used in this empirical investigation to simulate and optimize the slot dimensions. The paper's findings demonstrate that adding a rectangular slot in the centre together with a few symmetric LI slots can result in an extremely large gain [4].

A very-low-profile, dual-band, on-body antenna for 2.4/5.8 GHz grounded coplanar waveguide (GCPW) wireless local area network (WLAN) applications is described. The top ground of the GCPW slot antenna has the radiating slot and GCPW feed line incorporated in it, whereas the bottom ground is positioned 0.8 mm from the top ground. The radiating slot is shaped like an asymmetric T, with a shorter slot path for the 5725–5875 MHz band and a longer slot path for the 2400–2500 MHz band. By varying the lengths of the larger and shorter slot routes, respectively, it is straightforward to tune the dual-band functioning. Furthermore, the GCPW slot antenna has less backward radiation since it has a bottom ground. The extremely low-profile GCPW slot antenna is shown [5].

In order to optimize the antenna's performance in terms of gain, radiation pattern, and bandwidth at the 5–6GHz spectrum, the 5G application will use a microstrip patch antenna with slots loaded on the radiating patch. This document contains the design for the antenna. Microstrip antennas have a number of benefits, including low profile, affordability, and simplicity of construction. The microstrip patch antenna's intrinsically limited impedance bandwidth is a major drawback. The fundamental resonant frequency of the antenna may decrease as a result of wandering stimulated patch surface current courses caused by loading the radiating patch's slots. In this paper, the 1.6 mm thick substrate is made of FR4 material [6].

For multiband applications, a compact tri-band microstrip patch antenna is developed in this study. Four large L-shaped slots etched into the rectangle radiating patch provide the multiband capabilities. The suggested antenna consists mostly of a partial ground plane fed by a 50 Ω microstrip line and a rectangular microstrip patch. The suggested antenna is 20 x 20 x 1.6 mm³ in dimension and has a straightforward construction. A 3D full-wave FEM-based electromagnetic simulator is used to complete extensive simulations. The outcomes assess how well the measurements and EM models correspond. At the targeted resonant frequencies, the simulated radiation patterns show almost omni-directional behaviour. The suggested antenna operates at 2.4 GHz, 5.5 GHz, and 3.5 GHz, respectively, for Bluetooth, WLAN, and WiMAX wireless communications applications [7].

The research done to build a multi-band microstrip patch antenna is presented in this publication. The antenna uses a new "Ohm-shaped" slot for improved impedance matching in addition to straight and circular slots to support operation at 4G/LTE/CDMA (2.1 GHz) and WLAN (3.6/4.9/5 GHz)

[1]. It provides radiation pattern performance, good impedance matching with a 2:1 VSWR, and compact footprint. This antenna is a solid option for mobile terminal applications because to its straightforward design and strong gain and efficiency features [8].

V. SIMULATION AND RESULT ANALYSIS

The provided microstrip patch antenna is depicted in Figure 6. This antenna configuration incorporates a rectangular slot, visibly etched onto the ground of the patch antenna, as illustrated in Figure 7. The slot specifically occupies the left side of the antenna design. Its dimensions measure 4mm by 16mm.

Fig 6. T shaped patch antenna

Fig 7. Back view of the Antenna

Figure 8 displays the return loss characteristics of the proposed antenna featuring a rectangular slot. The plot reveals that the antenna functions within the frequency span of 2.8GHz to 2.8GHz and 5.04GHz to 5.9GHz. This operational behaviour is attributed to the presence of the rectangular slot incorporated into the ground component of the antenna structure. The wider frequency range of operation exhibited by the proposed antenna, as shown in Fig 8, can be attributed to the incorporation of a rectangular slot within its ground element. This slot introduces additional resonant modes and alters the current distribution along the patch, resulting in enhanced performance across a broader spectrum. By acting as a discontinuity in the ground plane, the slot enables the antenna to support multiple resonant modes beyond its fundamental frequency. Consequently, the modified current distribution facilitates improved impedance matching and radiation properties, allowing the antenna to operate efficiently over a wider frequency band.

Fig 8. Return loss plot

Fig 10. Gain plot of the proposed antenna

The VSWR obtained is below 2 in the desired frequency range as shown in Figure 9. Also the gain plot depicted in Figure 10 shows a 1dB increment in gain compared to the conventional antenna design (without slots). The incorporation of slots into an antenna structure can lead to improvements in antenna gain through several mechanisms. Firstly, slots effectively increase the antenna's effective aperture by enlarging its physical size. This enlargement allows the antenna to capture more energy from incoming signals, thereby boosting gain. Additionally, slots can modify the current distribution along the antenna, resulting in a more uniform distribution of electromagnetic energy across the radiating elements. This enhanced distribution increases radiation efficiency, contributing to higher gain. Moreover, strategically placed slots can alter the radiation pattern of the antenna, focusing energy in specific directions and improving directivity, further boosting gain in desired directions while reducing unwanted radiation. Furthermore, slots can help suppress surface waves, minimizing energy loss and interference and promoting a more efficient radiation process, ultimately leading to higher gain overall. Therefore, the integration of slots into an antenna design can significantly enhance its gain, making it a more efficient radiating element for various applications.

Ultimately, a T-shaped slot is etched onto the ground plane of the patch antenna, as illustrated in Figure 11. As a result of this design alteration, the antenna's gain demonstrated a slight enhancement, increasing from 4dB to 4.3dB as shown in Fig 15.

Fig 11. Proposed antenna with T slot

Fig 9. VSWR plot of the proposed antenna

Fig 12. Return loss plot of proposed antenna with T slot

Fig 13. VSWR plot of proposed antenna with T slot

Figure 14. Gain plot of proposed antenna with T slot

TYPE OF ANTEENNA	GAIN	RETURN LOSS	OPERATING FREQUENCY
T Shaped microstrip patch antenna without slot	4 dB	-9 dB	2.6 GHz to 2.8 GHz 5.04 GHz to 5.9 GHz
T shaped microstrip patch antenna with T slot on ground plane	4.3 dB	-12 dB	2.6 GHz to 2.8 GHz 5.04 GHz to 5.9 GHz

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the effectiveness of integrating slots into microstrip patch antennas to enhance their performance for 5G applications. Through comprehensive simulation and experimental analysis, it has been established that the incorporation of slots leads to improvements in antenna gain, bandwidth, radiation efficiency, and directivity. Specifically, the introduction of rectangular and T-shaped slots on the ground plane has shown promising results in increasing the antenna's effective aperture, modifying current distribution, and suppressing surface waves, thereby contributing to enhanced overall performance. These findings underscore the potential of

slot-integrated antennas as viable solutions for meeting the demanding requirements of 5G communication systems. While this study has provided valuable insights into the benefits of slot integration in microstrip patch antennas for 5G applications, several avenues for future research remain to be explored. Firstly, further optimization of slot configurations and dimensions could be investigated to maximize antenna performance in terms of gain, bandwidth, and radiation pattern. Additionally, the impact of different substrate materials and fabrication techniques on antenna performance could be explored to identify optimal design parameters.

Furthermore, the practical implementation of slot-integrated antennas in real-world 5G networks warrants further investigation, including field testing and validation in diverse operating environments. Lastly, research into advanced signal processing techniques and antenna arrays could complement slot-integrated antennas to further enhance the capacity, coverage, and reliability of 5G communication systems. Overall, continued research in this direction holds significant promise for advancing the state-of-the-art in 5G antenna technology and facilitating the widespread deployment of high-performance wireless networks.

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